

BIOREMEDIATION: ROLE OF MICROALGAE IN NITROGEN REMOVAL

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Annotation: *The presence of nitrogen in water is a major environmental problem nowadays caused by agricultural and industrial activities. The content of nitrogen, phosphates, ammonia, and other inorganic compounds in reservoirs harms their ecosystem, water quality, and the environment. Recently, the study and use of water bioremediation methods using microalgae has become relevant. This method has proven to be an environmentally friendly and cheap way to purify water.*

*This paper examines the techniques used to remove nitrogen from waste water, focusing on the use of microalgae called *Chlorella vulgaris*. This microorganism is able to absorb inorganic nitrogen and phosphates from water, using them for its own growth. Currently, *Chlorella* is considered as a suitable method for wastewater treatment under various conditions, including low temperatures and different types of pollution.*

Key words: *bioremediation, microalgae, nitrogen removal, wastewater treatment, eutrophication, *Chlorella vulgaris*, phycoremediation, consortium of microalgae and bacteria.*

Introduction

Nitrogen is a critically important nutrient, but its excessive presence in waters can be risky for the environment and living organisms. Agricultural, industrial industry, as well as urbanization annually contribute to an increase in the content of ammonia, nitrates and organic nitrogen in water systems. This reduces the level of dissolved oxygen, worsens the condition of water systems and also causes a process called eutrophication. Eutrophication is the excessive enrichment of water in reservoirs with nutrients, which accelerates the reproduction of algae and cyanobacteria and ultimately leads to an imbalance of the aquatic ecosystem. According to UNEP, about 80% of wastewater worldwide is released into the environment without proper treatment, leading to river pollution (UNEP, 2016). An excess of nitrogen in the consumed water can cause the development of thyroid cancer, stomach and diabetes. For plants, there is a risk of late maturation and an increase in the growth period. The classical method of biological nitrogen purification includes the stages of nitrification and denitrification, requiring intensive aeration and the addition of organic carbon from external sources. Aeration costs can reach 45-75% of the total energy consumption of wastewater treatment plants (Wang et al., 2022). In addition, the classical method has other disadvantages: the formation of silt and slurry, membrane contamination, the formation of toxic products, limited sampling, the release of NO₂, which leads to the greenhouse effect, and expensive maintenance.

To solve the problem of water purification from nitrogen, the use of microalgae that absorb pollutants is being considered. The use of *Chlorella* is beneficial for itself, because microalgae require nitrogen, phosphorus, CO₂ and light for their own autotrophic growth. *Chlorella vulgaris* is used in bioremediation because of its great effectiveness in improving water quality in accordance with required standards.

Mechanisms of nitrogen assimilation by microalgae

Ammonium is the preferred form of nitrogen for microalgae, as it is absorbed without prior reduction through the GS-GOGAT enzyme pathway: glutamine synthetase attaches NH₄⁺ to glutamate to form glutamine, after which glutamate synthase (GOGAT) transfers the amino group to α -ketoglutarate, reproducing two glutamate molecules. This is how inorganic nitrogen is incorporated into the amino acid reserve of the cell (Wu et al., 2019).

Nitrates are absorbed in a more energy-intensive way: nitrate reductase in the cytoplasm reduces NO₃ to nitrite, after which nitrite reductase in chloroplasts completes the reduction to ammonium, which then reacts with GS-GOGAT (Daniel-Vedele et al., 1998). At the same time, in crops with a high density of algae, under the influence of photosynthesis, the pH of the medium can

rise to 9.5-11, shifting the $\text{NH}_4^+/\text{NH}_3$ equilibrium towards volatile ammonia. This phenomenon, called ammonia distillation, also affects the absolute removal of nitrogen, although it is an undesirable mechanism for the environment (Garcia et al., 2000).

Fig. 1. Enzymatic pathways of nitrogen assimilation: GS-GOGAT cycle (glutamine synthase/glutamate synthase) and glutamate dehydrogénase (GDH) pathway

Nitrogen removal efficiency in various systems

The effectiveness of microalgae crops is largely determined by their species composition and method of application. In the laboratory, when using a batch photobioreactor, a microalgae called *Scenedesmus quadricauda* removed ammonium nitrogen at the level of 83.5%. At the same time, *Chlorella vulgaris* provided higher total nitrogen removal due to its ability to use both ammonium and nitrates at different growth stages (Zheng et al., 2025). For *Nannochloropsis* sp. complete nitrogen removal was established at initial concentrations below 40 mg N/l, and at concentrations of 40-80 mg N/l, the degree of removal reached 95% (Raykov et al., 2011).

Ponds with a high rate of algae growth (HRAP) are the most practically scalable technology. These are open reactors with a depth of 0.2-0.5 m with a mixing blade with a speed of 0.15-0.3 m/s and access to natural light. HRAP is capable of removing up to 90% ammonium, 70% COD and 50% phosphates from wastewater at an average hydraulic load of about 7.7 days (Villacrés et al., 2024). Studies of two experimental HRAPS in Barcelona showed an average annual nitrogen removal of 73% and 57%, taking into account different retention times. The main purification mechanisms were ammonia distillation (47% and 32% of the total removal) and assimilation by algae cells (26% and 25%) (Garcia et al., 2000). Studies in Ethiopia, taking into account the tropical climate, showed a maximum total nitrogen removal of 91.7% with 8 days of retention and a pond depth of 300 mm (Ambaw et al., 2018).

Closed photobioreactors provide precise control of the conditions of algae maintenance and cultivation, which contributes to an increase in nitrogen removal efficiency by up to 90%. Such reactors are used when working with highly concentrated industrial effluents, but they have a high cost of construction and maintenance.

Consortia of microalgae and bacteria

Under real-world operating conditions, open systems contain mixed microbial communities. It has been proven that mixed consortia of microalgae and bacteria are superior to individual monocultures in total nitrogen removal. From a physiological point of view, symbiosis is possible due to the exchange of metabolites between organisms: microalgae produce oxygen through photosynthesis, providing nitrifying bacteria with the necessary oxidizer, bacteria in turn return CO_2 and support photosynthesis in microalgae. This symbiosis is able to reduce the total energy consumption of the system by 40-60% compared to mechanical aeration (Huang et al., 2022).

A study of the interaction of *Chlorella vulgaris* with nitrifying activated sludge showed that due to the ratio of 10% algae to 90% sludge, complete removal of ammonium nitrogen in 7 days is possible. Such a result is impossible in a monoculture (Sepehri & Sarrafzadeh, 2020). In another experiment, reactors with microalgae-bacterial organisms with periodic loading (MB-SBR) achieved a total nitrogen removal of 66.74% with simultaneous nitrification and denitrification (Jin et al., 2023). The available data indicate that the joint cultivation and use of bacteria and microalgae contributes to high rates of nitrogen purification from wastewater and makes this area a priority in practical use.

Limitations and prospects

Despite the scientifically proven potential, the widespread practical use of microalgae systems has some problems. One of the problems is the expensive cost of harvesting biomass: small algae cells (2-20 microns) in dilute suspensions (0.5 - 2 g/l) are difficult to precipitate. Each alternative approach - centrifugation, flocculation, flotation, and immobilization of cells in biofilms – has its own nuances in price or effectiveness (Abdelfattah et al., 2022).

Open systems are subject to contamination due to zooplankton (rotifers, protozoa) this negatively affects the growth and reproduction of the crop. To solve the problem, local and adapted strains are used. Also, seasonal variability of solar radiation and temperature significantly affect the performance of open ponds, which limits practical applications.

A key strategy for improving economic performance is the collection of biomass from wastewater treatment plants. Biomass grown on wastewater usually contains 32-42% protein, 18-23% carbohydrates, and 13-20% lipids – these are quite valuable raw materials for fertilizers, biogas, and feed additives (Correa et al., 2025). This integration will lead to resource recovery and significantly reduce the cost of the entire water treatment process.

Promising areas of research for optimizing work include: CO₂ supply to stimulate algae growth and suppress unwanted ammonia distillation; selection and genetic improvement of strains with increased resistance to ammonium and high nitrogen uptake rate; development of hybrid systems combining the advantages of open ponds (low costs) and closed bioreactors (productivity); creation of mathematical models for forecasting and optimizing the operation of systems in variable climatic conditions.

Conclusion

The use of microalgae is a biologically justified and technically feasible solution to the problem of wastewater treatment. Due to the direct absorption of ammonium and nitrates through the GS-GOGAT enzymatic pathway, rapid growth rate, metabolic plasticity and the ability to work in symbiosis with bacteria, they provide nitrogen removal at the level of 57-97% with much lower energy consumption compared to the traditional purification method. HRAP ponds have demonstrated good productivity and speed, as well as the potential for simultaneous biomass production. Consortia of algae and bacteria open up the possibility of combining nitrification, denitrification and photosynthesis in one reactor without using mechanical aeration.

Overcoming existing barriers, primarily in terms of biomass harvesting, crop stability, and regulatory issues of its use, will require cross—industry efforts at the intersection of microbiology, engineering, and environmental policy. At the same time, the integration of phycoremediation into the concept of circular bioeconomics, in which purified water and valuable biomass are complementary products of a single process, defines this approach as one of the most promising in sustainable water resources management in the coming decades.

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